

Bank Loan Approval System Using Machine Learning

Billan Jacob John
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
billanjacob314@gmail.com

Ankitha Philip
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
ankithaphilip@amaljyothi.ac.in

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Abstract— Loans are one of the prominent profit sources for banks. Banks grant loans after an intensive process of verification and validation. Even they still stand a risk of how likely is the borrower to repay the loan. So, loan application processing and approval is a tiring process manually done by banks. The Loan Prediction System makes this process effortless by using a Machine Learning model to predict whether an applicant's loan should be approved or rejected. This is done by assessing different attributes like age, gender, loan amount, applicant income, employment status etc.

Keywords—loan prediction, machine learning, Loan Prediction System

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world all financial dealings are done through internet. It gives people the freedom to use bank services from anywhere in the world at any time. Different types of loans are provided by a bank and the processing of applications is a tiresome process. A lot of time is spent by employees on reviewing applications to whether approve or reject an application. Loan amount, term, applicant income, co applicant income etc are analysed to find the possibility whether the applicant will repay the loan or not. Manually analysing this takes time and is difficult task.

Using a machine learning algorithm to analyse the application and predict whether to approve or reject applications will reduce the time consumed by employees. Data of previous applicants are used to build the ML model. The features of this data include gender, marital status, educational qualification, applicant income etc. The data set contains 615 applicant details. Training dataset and test dataset is split in the ratio 2:8. Ensemble algorithm is used to build ML model. Three ensemble algorithms are used and they include logistic regression, random forest and XGBoost. The training and test data is cleaned and fed to the model.

The model is implemented on a Banking System and the loan applications can be reviewed by Manager. The system collects data from the application and data base and use it on the ML algorithms. The final result is concluded from the prediction of these 3 models.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A bank's profit or a loss depends to a large extent on loans i.e, whether the customers are paying back the loan or defaulting [2]. By predicting the loan defaulters, the bank can reduce its Non-Performing Assets [2]. This makes the study of this phenomenon very important [2]. The historical data of

candidates was used to build a machine learning model using different classification algorithms [1]. The main objective of this paper is to predict whether a new applicant granted the loan or not using machine learning models trained on the historical data set [1]. It is tough and risky to check out manually every person and then recommended for loan approval [1]. A machine learning technique is used that will predict the person who is reliable for a loan, based on the previous record of the person whom the loan amount is accredited before [3]. The method in which two or more classifiers are combined together to produce an ensemble model for the better prediction [3]. They used the bagging and boosting techniques and then used random forest technique [4]. The problem of predicting the approval of a loan application is a classification problem, so the model is trained using classification algorithms like Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest Classifier and Support Vector Machine [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find whether to approve or reject a loan application using the data from database. Three ensemble models are build using test data set and is trained. The test and train data contain details of applications that were previously approved and rejected. The model should be able to correctly classify loan application to approve or reject.

Fig 1: Proposed Methodology

A. Data Collection and Cleaning

The required data is collected from Kaggle. The dataset contains details of previous loan applicants whose applications were approved and rejected. There are a total of 13 attributes in the data set which contains 614 columns. All insignificant features must be removed. The data set may contain null values and this cannot be fed to the algorithm, Fig. 2. Columns with null values should either be removed or filled with mean, median or mode.

```
import pandas as pd
data = pd.read_csv("data1.csv")
print(data.shape)
print("Null count \n",data.isnull().sum())
print(data.info)
```

```
(614, 13)
Null count
Loan_ID          0
Gender           13
Married          3
Dependents       15
Education        0
Self_Employed   32
ApplicantIncome  0
CoapplicantIncome 0
LoanAmount      22
Loan_Amount_Term 14
Credit_History  50
Property_Area   0
Loan_Status     0
dtype: int64
```

Fig 2: Dataset shape and null count

```
data['Gender'] = data['Gender'].fillna(data['Gender'].mode()[0])
data['Married'] = data['Married'].fillna(data['Married'].mode()[0])
data['Education'] = data['Education'].fillna(data['Education'].mean())
data['Dependents'] =
data['Dependents'].fillna(data['Dependents'].mode()[0])
data['Self_Employed'] =
data['Self_Employed'].fillna(data['Self_Employed'].mode()[0])
data['Property_Area'] =
data['Property_Area'].fillna(data['Property_Area'].mode()[0])
data['Loan_Status'] =
data['Loan_Status'].fillna(data['Loan_Status'].mode()[0])
data['LoanAmount'] =
data['LoanAmount'].fillna(data['LoanAmount'].median())
data['Loan_Amount_Term'] =
data['Loan_Amount_Term'].fillna(data['Loan_Amount_Term'].median())
data['Credit_History'] =
data['Credit_History'].fillna(data['Credit_History'].mean())
```

For skewed data using mean is not the best option as mean is affected by outliers or extreme values. In such cases median is used to fill null values. Mean and median can be

used for only numerical values, for categorical values mode is used.

The dataset contains both categorical and numerical values. Some algorithms work only on numerical and some only on categorical values. In such cases categorical values are converted to numerical values.

B. Algorithms used for prediction

1) Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a Supervised Learning technique that uses a set of independent variables to predict a categorical dependent variable. It's used to divide data into two or more categories. When linear regression is used to generate continuous values such as price, age, and so on, logistic regression generates a probability between 0 and 1, which is then used to categorise data.

2) Random Forest

Random forest is a combination machine learning algorithms, which are combined with a series of tree classifiers, with each tree casting a unit vote for the most popular class, and then combining the results to reach the final sort result [7]. Random forests have a high classification accuracy, can cope with outliers and noise, and never get overfit [7]. Random forests have become one of the most widely used research approaches in the data mining and biological fields [7].

3) XGBoost

XGBoost stands for Extreme Gradient Boosting, which is a more advanced version of Gradient Boosting Algorithm. Both XGBoost and Gradient Boost Algorithm are ensemble algorithms implements the principle of boosting weak learners using the gradient descent architecture. But, XGBoost improves upon the base GBM framework through systems optimization and algorithmic enhancements.

C. Feature importance from Coefficients

Feature importance is a technique used to evaluate the significance of various features on predicting target variables. Coefficients are found for each feature and it is used to calculate the feature score The higher the score, the more significant the feature is.

Fig 3: Feature importance

From the graph, credit_history is the most important feature. Education, Married, Self_Employed, Property_Area and Gender are some other important features.

D. Database

The data required to predict is retrieved from the database. When a new application is applied details like loan amount, term etc. are inserted into loan table.

To view the prediction of new application necessary features are fetched from both loan table and customer table.

TABLE I. LOAN

Variable Name	Description	Type
loanno	Unique id used to identify applications	Integer
loanamount	Amount applied for in the loan	Float
term	Duration of loan	Integer

TABLE II. CUSTOMER

Variable Name	Description	Type
gender	Male or female	Character
married	Whether married or not	Character
dependents	Number of dependents on the applicant	Integer
education	Graduate or non-graduate	Character
self_employed.	Self-employed or not	Character
Applicant_income	Monthly income of applicant	Decimal
Coapplicant_income	Monthly income of co-applicant	Decimal
Credit history	Credit history of applicant	Integer
Property_area	Urban or Semi-urban or rural area	Char

IV. RESULTS

A. Model Evaluation

Three ensemble models- Logistic Regression, Random Forest and XGBoost is used to build the prediction system. The accuracies of the three models are:

- Logistic Regression: 0.86
- Random Forest: 0.85
- XGBoost: 0.81

The mode of three results from the models is the final result.

B. Loan Application Reviewing

All pending/processed applications can be viewed through the web app. Pending applications can be approved or rejected through the same.

Fig 4.1: All Loan Applications

Fig 4.2: View application

Fig 4.3: View prediction

Fig 4.4: Application approved

V. CONCLUSION

Banks will benefit from the system since it makes loan application assessment and approval easier and faster. The use of ensemble model has helped in increasing the accuracy of prediction. The best accuracy obtained is 0.86 by logistic regression.

Only prior applicants' data is used to train the current system. It can be improved in such a way that after an applicant is approved or rejected, it updates the testing data with new applicant data. This way the system learns and improves itself. Cibil score, which will become the highest significant feature can also be integrated with the system.

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